

The study in question will be referred to as [G2024](#)

To the Authors: Your [Figure 2](#) contradicts your study and raised questions (3) and (4). Can you also take a look at all the other questions ((1),(2),(5))?

Design questions and two potential fatal design flaws

A survival model assumes that a patient dropping out (censoring) has nothing to do with the disease being studied. [G2024](#) chose fever duration as the primary endpoint and censored GAS complications. **The causative association between GAS complications and prolonged fever is already established, which seems to already invalidate [G2024](#).** Since the study was already conducted, we can check whether, and to what degree, informative censoring affected it: all 8 GAS complications (6 in placebo, 2 in control) were recorded within the first 48-72 hours, which raises a question, whether most, if not all complications happened while the patient was febrile and regressing.

(1) How many out of recorded 8 treatment failures occurred after fever cessation?

(2) How were treatment failures, withdrawals, and other interruptions of temperature follow-up incorporated into the fever-duration ITT analysis? Specifically, was fever duration recorded as the last temperature assessment before interruption, or was another rule used?

If fever duration was recorded as the last temperature assessment before interruption, then the following applies:

The primary continuous endpoint is "fever duration".

Per-Protocol (PP): Excludes treatment failures. Data from the 13% of placebo patients who failed treatment is gone.

Intention-to-Treat (ITT): A patient withdrawn due to a retropharyngeal abscess is indistinguishable from a patient whose fever naturally ceased at the same time in regard to the primary endpoint. Let's simulate this scenario with [G2024](#)'s design:

Placebo: 100 patients. At $t = 0$, all febrile. At $t = 12h$, 99 patients removed due to retropharyngeal abscess, 1 patient afebrile

Control: 100 patients. At $t = 0$, all febrile. At $t = 12h$, 100 patients afebrile

Conclusion: placebo proven to be non-inferior to amoxicillin in both PP and ITT in the primary endpoint.

The flaw above alone would render [G2024](#) incapable of verifying its own hypothesis in ITT.

Analysis errors, discrepancies and questions

Mismatched confidence intervals and GAS-positive subgroup

[G2024](#):

In the subgroup analysis of culture-confirmed patients, the mean difference in fever duration was 6.61 h (95% CI, - 4.5 to 17.7)

Interestingly, in the subgroup analysis of culture-confirmed GAS pharyngitis, the reduction in fever duration was greater (up to 17.7 h), thus suggesting a better efficacy of amoxicillin in culture-confirmed cases. However, this finding raises concerns about potential false positives among rapid antigen detection tests, which could dilute the effect of amoxicillin in cases of viral origin. The GAS

rapid antigen detection tests may be falsely positive because of cross-reaction (e.g., with *Streptococcus milleri*) [33–35].

False positives qualifying for the study work **in favor** of placebo non-inferiority, not against it. Also, the **very study** authors claim near 100% specificity.

In addition, throat cultures may have been falsely negative because of non-viable GAS, resulting from suboptimal transport conditions of the swab specimen or growth inhibition by *Staphylococcus aureus* [34–37].

The more viable and dominant GAS is in the throat, the higher the probability of a true positive culture.

As the RADT was performed first, discomfort or opposition from the patient during the RADT might have led to less cooperation for the subsequent swab collection for culture, potentially compromising the quality of the sample and the detection of GAS by culture.

Greater throat pain severity increases the likelihood of refusing the swab, which biases the sample **in favor** of placebo non-inferiority

Nevertheless, this observation should be interpreted with caution because of the small sample size, which resulted in wider confidence intervals.

Let's take a look at confidence intervals:

Mean differences in fever duration are shown with 95% CI in 3 populations: per protocol intention to treat; and the subgroup of patients with culture-confirmed group A streptococcal pharyngitis.

Analysis	Mean difference	95 % CI	CI width	Group size
Per protocol	2.0	[-8.3 to 12.3]	20.6	65
Intention to treat	2.8	[-6.5 to 12.2]	18.7	88
Subgroup (per Figure 2)	6.0	[-1.7 to 14.3]	16	40-53
Subgroup (per text)	6.61	[-4.5 to 17.7]	22.3	40-53

Confidence interval of the **Subgroup** on the **Figure 2** was narrower than those from **PP** and **ITT**!

(3) Why is there a discrepancy between the **Figure 2** and the study text?

Per protocol group was between 22.6% and 62.5% larger than the **Subgroup** and yet it yielded a confidence interval only 8% narrower (or 28.75% wider), so the **Subgroup** has a better interval-group size ratio than **both** **PP** and **ITT** in **both** **Figure 2** and per text options.

(4) Can you confirm that the size of Subgroup was 53, or, if that was not the case, explain how it was constructed?

Absence of evidence fallacies

G2024's first conclusion :

Pain intensity and risk of complications were similar between the two groups

This is not just an absence of evidence fallacy. In order to claim it, one needs to ignore clear negative trends in the placebo arm.

	Placebo n/N (%)	Amoxicillin n/N (%)	Crude RR	95 % CI	p
Asthenia	15/34 (44)	4/31 (12)	3.42	1.27 – 9.20	0.006
Headache	5/34 (15)	1/31 (3)	4.56	0.56 – 36.9	0.20
Abdominal pain	6/34 (18)	1/31 (3)	5.47	0.70 – 42.9	0.10
School absence	12/34 (37)	6/31 (21)	1.82	0.79 – 4.27	0.17
Treatment failure	6/46 (13)	2/42 (4.76)	2.74	0.58 – 12.8	0.27
persistence of GAS at 1 month	12/18 (67)	3/20 (15)	4.44	1.49 – 13.26	0.0023

$P < 0.05$ likely emergence in most complications was hindered by study's early termination (n=88 vs. planned 198)

Asthenia was addressed:

However, this alone may not be sufficient to justify antibiotic therapy, especially considering that patients who experience this symptom may be relieved with symptomatic treatment.

Asthenia was not alone.

Treatment failure relative risk computation question

Treatment failure	RR	CI	P
Crude treatment failure	2.74	0.58 – 12.8	0.27
Treatment failure claimed in the study	2.15	0.44 – 10.57	0.1

(5) Can you please specify how (method, denominator set, and any correction used) the 2.15 RR was calculated?

Failed non-inferiority margins

G2024 second conclusion:

Placebo appears to be non-inferior to amoxicillin in reducing fever duration

Despite every listed potential masking, flaw, conflation, stretch, and error shifting the perceived results in the same direction (placebo non-inferiority), G2024 failed to meet its own criteria for success: the predefined non-inferiority margin was 12.0 hours. The reported 95% CI upper bounds are 12.3 hours (PP) and 12.2 hours (ITT). Both exceed 12.0.

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G2024's consequences on patient-doctor relationship

G2024 third and final conclusion:

These findings support the restrictive antibiotic treatment for streptococcal pharyngitis.

Antimicrobial stewardship is a valid and vital objective for which G2024 openly advocates for. This objective inherently introduces an ethical dilemma between individual patient recovery and the public health goal of slowing antimicrobial resistance.

The *watchful waiting* application introduces another conflict: it increases the number of medical consultations, which increases revenue of healthcare sector at the expense of patients and their parents. However minuscule and ignorable it may appear, in principle it exists.

For this reason, any study attempting to advocate for watchful waiting should be subjected to extraordinary scrutiny in order to not destroy patient-doctor trust.

The fact that in G2024 every masking, conflation, stretch (this comment covers a minority of observed stretches), and error shift the results in the same direction (placebo non-inferiority) does not help in sustaining said trust and it does not help antimicrobial stewardship initiative. The fact, that author of G2024 started working in European Journal of Pediatrics 6 months before publishing it also does not help.

If G2024 turns out to be unacceptable, as it seems to be, it would, aside from damaging quality of medical academia and status of European Journal of Pediatrics, maim aforementioned trust in the Swiss medical sector. The longer it stays published, the greater the damage.

Aside from the consequences to the children, we noted no regard given to reduced economic output of parents forced to stay at home with their children. Instead of expected heightened scrutiny, we did observe the opposite. Not only in G2024, but in its application, as it is cited by Swiss pediatricians in regard to children 0-2, while G2024 is about ages 3-15. This calls for additional caution from parents.